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Open Science Guidebook: Open Research Data

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Research data is the foundation of scientific knowledge and therefore widely also acknowledged to be a valuable outcome of research. It underpins the results of scientific research and enables derivation of theoretical or applied findings. The demand for open research data has grown rapidly as various funders, publishers and institutions increasingly require researchers to open their research data. Also, more mechanical, managerial, and technical handling of research data has increasingly become as important a part of a researchers work as methodological or analytical data processing. Therefore, there are several different issues associated with opening data, which researchers should consider during the entire research life cycle.

1. WHAT

At its purest, open research data refers to data that has been made freely and publicly accessible, modifiable, redistributable, and reusable for anyone and for any purpose free from technical, financial and legal barriers. However, not all research data can be made accessible and available without restrictions. Sensitivity and identifiability of the data, copyrighted content, and intentions to commercialize research results are some of the issues to consider with caution before publishing data. Therefore, data sharing is best to be guided by the now widely recognized and adopted principle of 'as open as possible and as closed as necessary'.

Proper research data management through all stages of a research project is the most important prerequisite for reusable open data. The purpose of research data management and its advance planning in a data management plan (DMP) is to ensure that the data remains accessible, reliable, securely protected, and reusable through its entire lifecycle. A DMP facilitates the consideration of all relevant aspects of data management, including the handling, organization, documentation, storage and backup, and opening of the data. An especially critical step in securing the reusability of data is sufficient documentation and description of its content and collection procedures, that is, metadata. Contextual metadata provides the necessary information to understand the data, including how it can or cannot be used. Furthermore, standardized and machine-readable metadata facilitates discoverability of the data. Poor documentation may render otherwise publicly available data useless for any further research, including one's own.

FAIR Data principles have been designed to facilitate data management planning from the perspective of the reusability of data and are now adopted as the cornerstone of data management requirements of many funders and research organizations. FAIR stands for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. Each item is accompanied by practical application instructions that provide guidance on how to achieve these through data management. However, it is important to distinguish FAIR data from 'Open data'. FAIR Data principles are intended to be modular in the sense that they may be followed in various combinations depending on the circumstances. If the data cannot be made publicly available, for instance because of its sensitivity, it can still be considered FAIR if data management is otherwise taken care of accordingly and metadata are made publicly accessible.

2. WHY

The core arguments for open research data are straightforward. Opening and sharing research data according to the FAIR principles supports transparency of research enabling its verification, replication, reproduction, and refinement, and advances reuse of data, which can potentially accelerate scientific progress. Open research data also benefits stakeholders outside academia and ensures greater returns from public investment in research. This way open data brings great benefits to society. Open data also reduces fraud in science and, on the other hand, increases the public's trust in science.

From a researcher's perspective, opening research data may enhance researchers' recognition and visibility in the field. Also, researchers may maximize the usefulness of the data itself and increase their own efficiency in conducting research. Properly managed research data creates a competitive edge and is an important part of a high-quality research process. When research data are open and reproducible, researchers can build on previous knowledge, achieve better and diverse conversations across research fields, make unexpected discoveries and increase opportunities for new collaborations. Managing and opening research data according to FAIR principles improve its long-term availability even for researcher's own purposes. Consequently, it is important that research data is openly available so that it is possible to return to it with new methods or different points of view. With constantly evolving new methods, it is possible to make sure that there are no errors in the previous analysis.

3. HOW

For those who are interested in generating or sharing open research data, it would be useful to note the following points:

Data Management Planning

- Research data management (RDM) is a process in which need to be invested time and resources and it consists of several components such as knowing and describing your data, following ethical and legal principles, and understanding the workflows related to securing, storing, sharing, archiving, opening, and publishing your data, which must be considered at different stages of the research process.
- A data management plan (DMP) is a useful tool that helps you to plan, collect and archive your data efficiently and systematically.
- When generating open research data, try to put yourself in someone else's shoes so in the end your data will be well documented for the further use of others and your future self.
- To make research replicable, reproducible or reusable research data should be as open and FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) as possible, while considering for ethical, commercial and privacy constraints with sensitive data or proprietary data.
- Sometimes the data cannot be opened for example because the researcher is not the owner of the data in the first place, or the data is too sensitive to being published. Even though, whatever the reason is, it is always possible to open the description of the data (metadata) because the fact that the existence of the data is known is essential from the point of Open Science.

Ethical and legal considerations

- It is good to note that 'research data' means different things to different disciplines and not all research data can be made available without restrictions.
- In research involving human participants, disclose your plans of opening the data in the participant information sheet, and obtain the participants' express consent to retain and share the data with the consent form.
- Data anonymization helps you to protect sensitive data and the anonymized data is not subject to protection regulations.

Long-term preservation and sharing

- Licenses, such as Creative Commons (CC), can be applied to any material (e.g., sound, text, image, multimedia, software) where some exploitation or usage rights exist, and it would be important to use standardized licenses also to your research data.
- The recommended way to store and to share data is to deposit in a trustworthy online repository permanent accessibility and storage of the research data.
- Both discipline-specific and cross-disciplinary data repositories exist. Some examples of widely used generic data repositories are e.g., Zenodo and Open Science Framework (OSF).
- When selecting a repository for your data, prefer certified repositories and ensure that repository of your choice provides data with a persistent identifier (PID), such as digital object identifier (DOI), which facilitates searching, discovery, reuse, and citing of your research data.
- Be mindful of your institution's policies and recommendations regarding the preferred repositories and long-term preservation and sharing your research data.

RESOURCES AND FURTHER READING

- European data strategy 2020: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0066&from=EN>
- Know Your Data – Research Data Management (RDM) (2021) Vol. 3 No. 1. <https://journals.helsinki.fi/thinkopendigest/issue/view/145>
- Open Knowledge Foundation: Open Data Handbook <http://opendatahandbook.org/>
- Creative Commons website: <https://creativecommons.org/choose/>
- Wilkinson, M.D. *et al.* (2016) 'The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship', *Scientific Data*, 3(1), p. 160018. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.

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